

NEWFEED

Turn Food Industry By-products into Secondary Feedstuffs via Circular-Economy Schemes

Grant Agreement number: 2013, Call 2020 Section 1 Farming IA

Dissemination and Communication Plan

Deliverable number 1.8

Work Package 1	Alternative feed value chains appraisal through a multi-actor approach
Task 1.3	Dissemination & Consumers Awareness
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Foreword

The work described in this report was developed under the project NEWFEED: Turn Food Industry By-products into Secondary Feedstuffs via Circular-Economy Schemes (Grant Agreement number: 2013/ Call 2020 Section 1 Farming IA). If you wish any other information related to this report or the NEWFEED project please visit the project web-site (www.newfeed-prima.eu) or contact:

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D1.8) is an update version of D1.7 (submitted on M36), D1.6 (submitted on M18) and D1.5 (submitted on M6), which presented the dissemination and communication plan for the NEWFEED Project. Specifically, D1.5 provided the overall project dissemination and communication strategy as well as the key stakeholders, the communication channels, the messages and the monitoring and evaluation mechanism, while a detailed description of the communication and dissemination activities that will take place during the lifetime of the project implementation were also presented. D1.6 and D1.7 are the updated versions of the D1.5, summarizing the progress of the dissemination and communication strategy at different periods of the project lifetime (D1.6 for the period M6 – M18 and D1.7 for the period M18 – 36) based on the KPIs that have been set.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Project aim

NEWFEED overall objective is to develop and adopt alternative animal feeds, setting up a circular economy approach in the livestock production by turning food by-products into high value secondary feedstuff for animal feed and to increase the Mediterranean livestock sustainability by valorizing local food industry by-products to reduced environmental impact and costs.

Three value chains in the Mediterranean area will be validated to create new business opportunities based on a multi-actor approach in their conception, configuration, and its sustainability assessment:

- The 1st case study will assess the use of grape stem from wineries as a second-generation feedstuff to produce a new feed ingredient for ruminants (dairy sheep and cattle). This case study is led by AZTI and tested in Spain.
- The 2nd case study will assess the use of orange peel from orange juice industry to produce an improved feed ingredient for ruminants (dairy sheep). This case study is led by NTUA and tested in Greece.
- The 3rd case study will assess the use of olive cake from olive oil industry to produce an improved feed ingredient for poultry (broiler chicken). This case study is led by HUSD and tested in Egypt.

Within this framework, the specific objectives for the project are to:

- Optimize and scale-up three new feed ingredients from winery, orange juice, and olive oil industry by-products. The processing will include solid fermentation and enzymatic hydrolysis to improve their nutritional value and digestibility and enhanced drying processes to stabilize them and foster their feed safety, security and shelf - life.
- Test and validate the entire value chain for three case studies with a multi-actor approach strategy (by-product generation, collection, processing-stabilizing, feed formulation, animal husbandry, consumer acceptability, sustainability, and regulatory aspects), which will help the adoption of new feed sources by livestock systems.
- Validate three intermediate ingredients and the final diets with animal feeding trials (TRL 6-7).
- Assess the sustainability of the new value chains from the environmental, economic, and social point of view.
- Define the market replicability of each value chain in the Mediterranean area (business models, road maps).
- Communicate and disseminate the project results and developments to the relevant stakeholders.

1.2 Communication & Consumers Awareness

Task 1.3 aims to define the Communication and Dissemination Plan of the project. More specifically, Task 1.3 aims at:

- raising visibility of the project and the public awareness on sustainability, circular economy, resource efficiency, neutral climate, food system interconnexion, local innovation, economic growth, jobs in rural or renewable biological resources,
- facilitating communication and sharing of knowledge among partnership and establishing the projects' communication & dissemination strategy, and
- developing targeted activities for the communication and dissemination of project achievements.

The Communication and Dissemination plan contains the procedures and methods to be followed for the communication of project objectives and results as well as the overall strategy for dissemination. A clear communication & dissemination strategy is established from the first days of the project, and it will be followed by the necessary adjustments for the whole project lifetime. The Communication and Dissemination Plan describes the aim and scope, identifies the target audiences, describes the communication channels used and it maps the networking activities developed with other projects initiatives.

2. Dissemination and Communication and strategy

2.1 Overall objectives

The NEWFEED Dissemination and Communication Plan and forthcoming activities will ensure that the project achievements will be widely disseminated to the target audience, at appropriate times and via appropriate channels, and that external stakeholders who can contribute additional value to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of these achievements can be identified and encouraged to participate.

The main objectives of NEWFEED's Dissemination and Communication Plan are:

- to increase the visibility of the project and disseminate the achieved results,
- to trigger the interest and attention of wider public and consumers on the solutions provided by the project,
- to generate awareness and engage stakeholders to the exploitation and valorization of food industry by-products, and
- to develop a collaborative network among different related projects, companies, and stakeholders for sharing experiences and results.

Communication and dissemination activities are an essential part of project actions, which are designed to inform the stakeholders of the relevant value chains and the public about the goals and outcomes of NEWFEED project. The overall communication objectives of the project are:

- Development of Project Identity & Branding.
- Development of Promotional Materials.
- Launching and maintaining Project Website.
- Establishment of Project Social Media presence.
- Facilitation of Media Coverage.
- Publication of project results in scientific journals, magazines, etc. and presentations in conferences and events.
- Organization of Demonstration Workshops at National and Mediterranean level.
- Networking with other projects and initiatives.

2.2 Strategy Approach

The NEWFEED Dissemination & Communication Plan is based on the following 4-stages methodology:

1st Stage: Why to disseminate? (Aim & Scope)

A project with high visibility and active interaction with key stakeholders will facilitate the effective dissemination of its outcomes. Providing the target audience with advance notice of future activities will increase its awareness, it will create links with the project, and it will establish and reinforce a wider networking activity. It is very crucial to promote the project results outside the partnership for the following reasons: i) the project results will be fully exploited in the most effective manner; ii) the knowledge and information gained through the project, can be made available to the food sector stakeholders; iii) the project achievements and solutions can be reused and replicated in other projects, becoming a reference point triggering further developments in the field and beyond; v) the project results will bring value and benefits to society in general.

2nd Stage: What to disseminate?

This stage is dealing with the appropriate selection of the project information capable for dissemination, on a clear and obvious way and keeping in mind the protection of specific part of knowledge so as not to endanger the results exploitation. Taking these under consideration, the following will be disseminated: i) Aim, objectives and key facts of the current situation concerning the exploitation of food industry by-products ii) Achievements and results iii) Events promotion and results i) Ready for use solutions, along with lessons-learned and recommendations, ii) Demonstration sessions on the new solutions.

3rd Stage: What are the target groups for dissemination?

Starting from the participating countries (Spain, Greece, Egypt and Turkey) the NEWFEED project will be demonstrated to the stakeholders of the food, feed and livestock sector in the whole Mediterranean area. More specifically the target groups are:

- Public Authorities and administrations in charge of managing, planning and regulating the environmental policies within the food value chain.
- Scientific community involved in food chain sustainability research due to its role in developing knowledge guidelines and best practices.
- Investors and relevant professionals that can develop business opportunities within recovery of food waste value chain or the production of animal feed.
- Food, feed and livestock companies.
- Organizations focused on environmental protection due to their potential to disseminate and support these types of initiatives.
- The society to increase environmental awareness about climate change and to create a more sustainable society.

4th Stage: How to disseminate?

Given that the target groups identified cover the whole food, feed and livestock sector, a different approach is necessary for each target group. At the same time, the usage of specific social media, such as Twitter and LinkedIn and the dedicated website play an important role, for the dissemination of the project and its results, promoting possible future cooperation but even more providing real feedback over the circulation of project and a valuable participants' data bank for future projects. The methods and channels will prepare for the scaling-up of the project solutions and will allow for getting the market ready for their use.

The focus for Year 1 will be to raise awareness of the project's objectives, expected results and general impact. In the second and third year a more targeted approach will be followed, with the aim to create synergies with other similar projects and engage stakeholders more actively. During the final year dedicated demonstration workshops will take place to ensure the diffusion of proposed solutions while special focus will be given to the development of a continuation strategy to follow up the exploitation strategy. To ensure effective implementation of the plan, all project partners will be involved in the planned Dissemination and Communication activities, under the guidance of SEVT, which will ensure that the project activities and results will be widely shared among the identified stakeholders in time and through the most appropriate channels.

3. SWOT Analysis of enabling environment for communication and dissemination

The SWOT Analysis presents the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the environment in which the communication and dissemination activities will be performed. The recognition of the current situation and the factors which will affect the communication and dissemination strategy will enable the development of targeted actions and will lead in better results. The purpose of the analysis is to become aware of the potential and barriers to better plan the strategic approach. The SWOT analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table1: SWOT analysis of NEWFEED communication environment

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transnational character of the project – implementation in 4 countries. • Topic in line with the main strategies of EU & UN (Green Deal, F2F & SDGs). • Meeting a market demand for advanced exploitation of agri-food by-products • Credibility offered by the financing of PRIMA Programme. • Partners composition which covers effectively all the participating countries. • The number of case studies and end-users ensures a widespread reach and visibility. • Experience of partners in organizing dissemination and communication activities. • Networking with other projects and initiatives at national and European level. • The high pool of stakeholders which each partner carries in the project. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low recognition of project brand. • Lack of impact points and results that can be presented in the first 3 years. • The complexity of the scientific part of the project which sometimes is difficult to be understandable from the media and public. • The high level of technological knowledge risks generating a language which hinders understanding for non-technical stakeholders. • The lack of experience, of scientific partners mainly, to present the scientific results in layman manner. • The project information has been drafted in English and its transfer to the national languages leads sometimes in ambiguities. • The success of the communication and dissemination strategy depends on the effort of each partner at national level. • The decline of the monitoring activities for the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy. • The decline of communication and dissemination activities after the end of the project.
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novelty: project provides innovative solutions for the exploitation of by-products, especially for the area of North Africa. • Diffusion of innovative approaches and initiatives to the North African relevant industry sectors. • Development of networking activities and cooperation between South Europe and North Africa. Reach out to new markets and actors forming new constellations. • Improvement of relevant industry sectors image in both geographical areas. 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of attention from the relevant stakeholders • Covid-19 pandemic has limited the organization of big dissemination events. • Not reaching statistically significant input/feedback from stakeholders. • The non-effective understanding of the solutions provided from the relevant industry sectors.

The analysis shows that NEWFEED has a strong foundation on which to create impact, being an innovative and widely applicable project. The challenge will be to use resources wisely, giving the right people, the right information at the right time for maximum impact.

4. Communication and dissemination principles & objectives

To ensure maximum efficiency and impact of the dissemination and communication plan the abovementioned principles will be followed:

- **Flexibility:** the communication and dissemination strategy need to be flexible in order to adapt to the changing needs and challenges of the target groups and the environment that takes place.
- **Adaptability:** To maximize efficiency and impact to all target groups, the partnership will develop core messages tailored to the different target audiences while expressed in a relative context.
- **Exploitation:** it is important to exploit all the relevant synergies and networking to reach key audiences and to avoid a duplication of effort.
- **Multi-targeted communication:** The communication strategy will cover the entire project and will include a variety of tools and channels to cover effectively all the target groups.

The main communication objective of NEWFEED Dissemination & Communication Plan is the public recognition of NEWFEED brand in the 4 participating countries and beyond them among the selected target groups. The ultimate communication and dissemination objective is the better capitalization and exploitation of project outcomes for the benefit of society. Figure 1 presents the process for the progressive increase of communication and dissemination activities.

Figure 1: The process of communication and dissemination activities

4.1 Target groups - Stakeholders

The most crucial goal of NEWFEED Communication and Dissemination Plan is to identify the key target groups who will contribute to the project and influence its success. It is essential to understand the needs and the expectations of these stakeholders since each of them needs a different approach. Each stakeholder category has a different level of power in influencing, communication reach or decision making. In this context, the stakeholders which are more important to reach and engage, must be identified appropriately to assist with the dissemination of the project results to the right audience. Dissemination channels and materials must be created and developed accordingly to achieve maximum impact. The following target groups have been identified as critical for the project success:

- Food, feed and livestock companies
- Public Authorities and administrations in charge of managing, planning and regulating the environmental policies within the food value chain.
- Scientific community involved in food chain sustainability research due to its role in developing knowledge guidelines and best practices.
- Investors and relevant professionals that can develop business opportunities within recovery of food waste value chain or the production of animal feed.
- Organizations focused on environmental protection due to their potential to disseminate and support these types of initiatives.
- Media / Press
- Citizens / society, to increase environmental awareness about climate change and to create a more sustainable society.

The following table provides an overview of the stakeholders' description, importance and means to reach them.

Table 2: The Target Groups and the communication channels

Stakeholder - Target Group	Presentation	Importance	Communication channels
Food, feed and livestock companies	The producers of food products from which the by-products arise, the producers of feedstuff who are looking for new more sustainable sources of ingredients and the livestock producers who want to maximize the performance through the improvement of animals' diet.	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media • Demonstration workshops • Advisory boards • Newsletters • Leaflets • Info-events • Networking activities with other projects
Public Authorities and administrations in charge of managing, planning and regulating the	A critical target group for the exploitation of the project results and realization of the long-term impact of the project.	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media • Advisory boards • Info-events • Newsletters

environmental policies within the food value chain			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted communication with project results
Scientific community	This target group refers to research and academic organizations, scientific journals, committees, and other groups in research fields related to food, feed and livestock chain sustainability research due to its role in developing knowledge guidelines and best practices.	Medium to high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media • Info-events • Networking activities • Newsletters • Publications • Conferences & workshops • Networking activities with other projects
Investors and relevant professionals	This target group focuses on the organizations and professionals that can develop business opportunities within recovery of food waste value chain or the production of animal feed	Medium to high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media • Demonstration workshops • Newsletters • Leaflets • Info-events
Organizations focused on environmental protection	These organizations have the potential to disseminate and support these types of initiatives	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media • Newsletters
Media & Press	Media & Press are crucial for the wide dissemination of project	Medium to high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media • Press Releases
Citizens / society	The focus in this group is to increase environmental awareness about climate change and to create a more sustainable society	Medium to high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website/social media/ Media

The categories of high importance consist of the major stakeholder groups that are directly interested in NEWFEED advances. Consequently, the approach to communication will be tailored to their needs and will engage them in future collaboration. The stakeholders list will be assessed and updated on a regular basis during the project.

4.2 Tailor made messages

A research project will be successful not only when it produces the expected research results but also when these results will be communicated through tailor made messages to the right audience. Tailored messages for the project, for the sustainability of agrifood, feed and livestock industry and for the circular economy approach will be developed. A set of specific and well understood messages (general, short general and tailored) are presented below.

Short General Message 1

NEWFEED will exploit food industry by-products for the development of alternative animal feeds both in South Europe and North Africa countries.

Short General Message 3

NEWFEED is a pioneer innovation initiative in the field of Food, Feed & Livestock producers, connecting 4 countries in 2 continents (Europe and Africa), led by AZTI a research center in Spain and funded by European Commission, via the PRIMA Programme.

Short General Message 5

The results of the NEWFEED project will be delivered by the end of 2025 and will contribute to the long-term competitiveness and sustainability of the livestock sector in South Europe and North Africa.

Short General Message 2

NEWFEED will make the European and the North-Africa agri-food sector greener and more sustainable:

- by implementing a set of innovative solutions to valorize the food industries by-products into high value secondary feedstuff for animal feed
- by promoting the approach of the circular economy into the agri-food supply chains and by providing solutions which can implemented in other by-products as well.

Short General Message 4

NEWFEED project is implemented in 4 countries:

- Spain
- Greece
- Turkey
- Egypt

NEWFEED project covers following sectors:

- Food (wine, fruits & juices & olive oil)
- Feed for food-producing animals (Ruminants, Dairy Cattles & Poultries)
- Livestock (Ruminants, Dairy Cattles & Poultries).

General Message

NEWFEED aims:

- to develop and adopt alternative animal feeds, setting up a circular economy approach in the livestock production by turning food by-products into high value secondary feedstuff for animal feed.
- to increase Mediterranean livestock sustainability by valorizing local food industry by-products to reduced environmental impact and costs.

Three value chains at the Mediterranean area will be validated to create new business opportunities based on a multi-actor approach in their conception, configuration and its sustainability assessment:

- the use of grape stem from wineries as a second-generation feedstuff to produce a new feed ingredient for ruminants (dairy sheep and cattle),
- the use of orange peel from orange juice industry to produce an improved feed ingredient for ruminants (dairy sheep),
- the use of olive cake from olive oil industry to produce an improved feed ingredient for poultry (broiler chicken).

The tailored key messages can be construed according to different target areas:

Food Industry - oriented message 1

NEWFEED provides high value alternatives for the recovery of food by-products by establishing synergies between food industries and feed and livestock sectors:

Outcomes to be presented:
- Valorisation strategies.

Valorisators - oriented message 2

NEWFEED provides new business opportunities within the recovery of food by-products value chain following the principles of circular economy.

Outcomes to be presented:
- Valorisation strategies.
- Business model

Feed & Livestock - oriented message 3

NEWFEED provides value-added alternative feeds that contribute to guaranteeing the supply of feed to livestock and, therefore, the sustainability of Mediterranean livestock farming.

Outcomes to be presented:
- Feeding strategies.

Commercially-oriented message

The exploitation of food industry by-products will create new business opportunities. NEWFEED will provide new business models and plans for the proposed valorization strategies.

Commercially-oriented message 2

NEWFEED will lead to the deduction of the cost of the specific livestock production, and it will increase the quality of the final products.

Commercially-oriented message 2

NEWFEED will reduce the dependence on imported raw materials for feed production.

Story-oriented message

NEWFEED solutions show that the circular economy approach is possible to the food and feed sector and leads to the development of high value secondary feeds which promote animal health and affect positively the quality of the final food products, without jeopardizing food and feed safety and satisfying consumers demands for more sustainable diets.

5. Communication channels and activities

5.1. Communication activities & channels

The presented Communication and Dissemination plan predicts the implementation of the following communication activities and channels:

Logo

By Month 3 the partnership released the official NEWFEED logo which represents the visible “brand” of the project. Logo was elaborated to include the concept of circular economy, food by-product and feed. The logo will be used in all material, actions and activities developed by project partners.

Project Website

The website is the main tool for communication and dissemination activities during project lifetime and after it. All the produced communication material, public deliverables, announcements for events will be posted in the website. Visiting the project site, the interested audience will get informed for the project, its progress, activities and achievements. All project deliverables, newsletters, multimedia and related articles will be posted on the website. SEVT is responsible for the creation and development of it and for the

update of the content with the contribution of all partners. To increase the traffic of the website, it will be shared for the social media of the project and the partners. The official URL of the project is www.newfeed-prima.eu .

Table 3. Structure, objectives, and content of NewFeed website.

Main sections	Sub-sections/ Objectives	Content
Home	Easy access to the main information about the project (case studies; involved beneficiaries; news & events).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reference to each case study with a link to direct visitors to a specific section with more details about each one. Easy access to events of the project with the development of a widget. An active section for the visitors to easily find our profiles in Twitter and LinkedIn. Newfeed partners, logos, and links for each one. Development of a widget in which the visitor can easily access Newfeed's Twitter feed.
About	Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A summary of the project scope and overall objectives. Presentation of each case study, description, and main goals. Direct link to each case study latest news and updates.
	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project methodology. Specific objectives.
	Impact	Presenting the impact in the framework of circular economy.
Partners	Introducing the Newfeed partnership	Each partner's logo with a direct link to its website.
News & Events	Dynamically changing section with news and events related to NewFeed project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> News about: each case study progress, announcements of publications (such as newsletters and project press releases) and in general news about the project (annual meetings, advisory boards etc.). Events: announcement of the upcoming events (conferences, workshops etc..) along with relevant information and participation links. Articles about the finished events, in which NewFeed project partners participated or organized with information about the outcomes, the participation etc. News about each case study would be easy to be found, by clicking the specific category.
	Informing the visitors about the latest news of the project related to each case study and announcements of publications.	
	Promoting the upcoming events and reporting those that have been performed.	
Media corner	Media kit	Communication material (Leaflet; Notice board; Roll up).
	Newsletter	Newsletters of NewFeed project with download option.
	Press Release	Press Releases of NewFeed with download option in English, Spanish, Greek, Turkish and Egyptian.
Stakeholders corner	Networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A reference to relevant projects to NewFeed by incorporating their logo, a link to their website

	A section dedicated to other projects related to NewFeed, allowing and promoting stakeholders' engagement and their participation to networking activities.	<p>and an executive description of each (start-end date, aim of the project etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A section for reporting clustering activities with other relevant projects. • Contact information for potential collaboration with other relevant projects.
	<p>Advisory board A section dedicated to the Advisory boards during NewFeed project to engage stakeholders and provide information about this action.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General information regarding the NewFeed Advisory boards. • Contact information for participation. • News about the performed Advisory Boards (participants, objectives, outcomes). • Information about the upcoming Advisory boards.
	<p>Demonstration workshops Providing information about this action. Promoting stakeholders' engagement.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General information and main goals of NewFeed Demonstration workshops. • Calendar of possible dates. • Contact point for participation. • Latest news on completed Demonstration workshops.
Outcomes	Public results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public deliverables of NewFeed project. • Videos presenting results of the project.
	Scientific articles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific articles published in open access and/or SCI journals with relevant details (authors names; title; DOI)
	Conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference to the conferences that the Newfeed partners would attend and present scientific results. • Information about the authors, title of presentation or poster, date, and the title of the conference • Access to the presentation, abstracts and posters developed and presented to each conference by Newfeed partners.
Contact us		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact information. • Easy access to Twitter and LinkedIn NewFeed profiles.

Partners' websites

The partners will create in their websites a section for the project where the main scope, the objectives and the expected results and the link to the project website will be presented. The funding source must be cited.

Press releases

Press releases will be published on the key milestones of the projects:

- Press release # 1: Kick of meeting of the project
- Press release # 2: Demonstration Workshops
- Press release # 3: Communication of the project outcomes

Press releases will be prepared in English, and they will be translated and adjusted in the languages of the project. SEVT will contact international media and one partner per country will be in charge of local media. SEVT in Greece, AZTI in Spain, METU in Turkey and Heliopolis University in Egypt. The PR produced in all languages will be uploaded on the project website. In specific cases local partners are free to prepare extra Press Releases, if needed, using the logo and the key messages of the project.

Press kit for media

Press kit will include all the basic information for the project and its aim is to be distributed to the media of the participated countries at any time and occasion. The Press kit will include:

- The presentation of the project.
- A short presentation of each partner.
- Statements from the companies of the project.
- The brochure of the project.

The content of the Press Kit was developed in English and each partner must adjust to local language. All versions will be published on the project website. The press kit for media (named Media kit) consists of the projects' leaflet, Notice Board and Roll-up.

Newsletter

Newsletters will be prepared and published on yearly basis. They will include information about the project status and progress, planned dissemination and communication activities, research work progress and the outcomes. The newsletter will be developed in english and each partner will decide if its nessecary to be translated or not. The Newsletter will be uploaded in project website and it will be spread from partners to all relevant stakeholders. SEVT will be responsible for the development of the Newsletter with the contribution of all partners.

Project Brochure

A brochure containing the basic information about the project was developed up to Month 6. The brochure was designed taking into consideration the logo and the project concept and it included the aim, the specific objectives, the expected outcomes, and the partnership as well as the basic data on financing and duration. It aims to increase the visibility of the project. Each partner will decide if it will be translated into its national language or not.

Outcomes' infographic

At the last six months of the project and in relation with the Demonstration Workshops an infographic will be prepared to present the concrete outcomes of the project. It aims to enhance the transferability of the project results. The infographic will be distributed during the Demonstration workshops in Europe and Africa. It will be drafted in English and each partner will decide if it will be translated in the national languages. All infographic variations will be published on the project website. The Infographic will be finalized by month 45 and will be distributed in electronic version or, if any, printed.

Roll-up

A Roll-up with the basic information of the project was developed after M12 to be used in live events and workshops. A version in English will be created and each partner will decide if it will be translated or not. At least one per country will be printed.

TWITTER account

A Twitter account [@NewfeedP](https://twitter.com/NewfeedP) was created and aims to maintain up-to-date communication regarding the project's progress, future activities, and active communication with interested parties. SEVT manages the Twitter account, and it will be the main focal point for the partners. At the same time each partner will be requested to contribute monthly regarding the events and/or meetings taking place in their country and to provide information for posting.

LINKEDIN page

A [Linkedin](#) page was created to publish technical-related news on NEWFEED and to catch the attention from researchers and the industrial stakeholders. SEVT manages the LINKEDIN page and the partners will be requested to contribute with posts on a monthly basis.

Notice Board

A Notice Board was developed which displayed at strategic places in all partners premises, accesible and visible to the public. The Notice Board will be maintained at least for 2 years after the end of the project. It was developed by SEVT and it contains the basic infos for the project (Title, objectives, beneficiaries, duration, budget, EC funding and PRIMA and project logo). The Notice Board was created at the first six months of the project implementation.

Presentation on conferences, workshops, food, feed and livestock sectors dedicated events

The partners will exploit any available opportunity to disseminate the project and its results in conferences, workshops and events. For this purpose, the presentation template of the project was created by SEVT, the first six months of the project, to be used by all partners. All the events to which the different partners attend to disseminate the project, will be communicated in advance to SEVT to be spreaded on the website and social media.

Publishing in journals, international congresses, newspapers and magazines

It will be followed by 2 types of publications: the first one concerns the scientific journals and international congresses where the universities and research centers of the partnership will publish their scientific work, in which there will always be reference at the project and the funding body and the second one concerns the publications in newspapers, magazines, etc where the industrial and business support partners will present the project and its results in a language friendly to the citizens. In both cases, the partners are required to notify SEVT of each dissemination act, in such a way as to allow these actions to be included in the main communication channels: NEWFEED website, twitter, linkedIn.

Electronic info-sheets on selected results to be disseminated

The last months of the project, when the results will have been finalized, electronic info-sheets will be developed to present the provided solutions in a catchable way to industrial partners mainly. These info-sheets will be disseminated in the Demonstration Workshop and will be sent to food, feed and livestock companies.

5.2 Project events

To effectively ensure the visibility of the project, to disseminate its results and to establish important liaisons, NEWFEED partners will organize several events, as described below.

Advisory board meetings

An Advisory Board (AB) acting as a knowledge sharing round table was set to analyze and validate the project objectives and results and the hurdles and bottlenecks of the whole value chain (raw material availability; valorization strategy; feed requirements; consumer awareness). The Advisory board consisted of 2-3 representative members of the main sectors or stakeholders involved in the recovery and exploitation of food by-products or potentially affected by the project's results:

- 1) Food companies
- 2) Logistic & valorization companies
- 3) Feed producers
- 4) Livestock
- 5) Public authorities and Policymakers
- 6) Research Organizations and Universities and
- 7) General public.

Table 4. Detailed information about the performed and upcoming Advisory Boards.

<u>ADVISORY BOARD</u>	DATE	OBJECTIVES	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
1 ST	15/12/2021	Description of the project scope and aims Analyse and validate the objectives and expected results of the project	13 PERSONS, 11 COMPANIES
2 ND	15/02/2023	Validate the proposed solution before the scaling up of the Valorisation strategies and Validation of alternative feeds	19 PERSONS, 17 COMPANIES
3 RD	12/06/2024	Get the stakeholders feedback about Exploitation Strategy. Encouraged them to participate in the new business activity.	11 PERSONS, 10 COMPANIES

Demonstration workshops

Three [Demonstration Workshops](#) at Region level were organized in each case study region (Spain, Greece, Egypt). The main objective is transnational knowledge transfer of project solutions. A special effort was made to demonstrate the potential of results to the food industries (wineries, orange juice and olive oil industry) and to end users of ingredients (cattle, sheep or poultry feed producers and livestock).

Specifically, one Demonstration Workshop at Mediterranean level was organized, inside the World Rural Forum focused on the replication of the proposed solution at Mediterranean level. Additionally, three national Workshops were conducted in Spain, Greece, and Egypt between months 33 to 45, to further support local-level replication.

Table 5. Detailed information about the planning of the Demonstration workshops.

DATE	ORGANIZER	PLACE	GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE	MAIN AUDIENCE	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
21/03/2024	UAGA	Mediterranean region	European	Food, feed and livestock companies	100
17/06/2024	NTUA	Greece	National		22
09/10/2024	HUSD	Egypt	National		23
26/03/2025	AZTI	Spain	National		75

5.3 Networking with other projects and initiatives

Partners have created a collaborative network among related projects to share experience and results. The focus was given to other projects (mainly H2020) and to international conferences and workshops. In the first year, projects and initiatives related to NEWFEED Project were recorded and in the next years the networking activities were organized. These activities included the presentation of the Project and its results in other projects' meetings, events, etc., the organization of joined workshops to increase synergies and participation in international congresses.

6. Monitoring and evaluation

6.1 Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination and networking activities

All dissemination and communication activities are closely monitored to ensure the successful implementation of the plan. The effectiveness of the NEWFEED Communication and Dissemination Plan will be evaluated every year during the lifetime of the project. The active contribution of all partners is very important for the implementation of the plan. SEVT, responsible for the development of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, is also in charge of monitoring its implementation. The communication and the dissemination plan's effectiveness will be evaluated based on the following KPIs.

Table 6: KPIs for the effectiveness of the Communication & Dissemination Plan

Communication Activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Visual Project identity (logo, Presentation templates, etc)	Create project visual identity. Final Logo & presentation & deliverable templates.	Revise visual identity if necessary	Revise visual identity if necessary	Revise visual identity if necessary
Project website & Partners' websites	Launch website & partners webpages	Update the website & the partners webpages	Update the website & the partners webpages	Update the website & the partners webpages
PRESS RELEASES	1 for the Kick-off meeting of the project. The PR will be drafted in English by SEVT and it will be sent to all partners to disseminate it in each national language.	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 for Demonstration Workshops (they will be developed from the organizers of the Workshops) • 1 for the communication of the project outcomes (it will be developed by SEVT in collaboration with AZTI, it will be sent to all partners to disseminate it in each national language). 	
PRESS KIT FOR MEDIA	Development of the Press Kit with	Update of the Press Kit with	Update of the Press Kit with	Update of the Press Kit with the

	the basic information for the project.	the results of the project	the results of the project	results of the project
NEWSLETTER	1 Newsletter (At least 250 receivers per country)	1 Newsletter (At least 250 receivers per country)	1 Newsletter (At least 250 receivers per country)	1 Newsletter (At least 250 receivers per country)
Project Brochure	Creation of Project Brochure & Dissemination (electronic or printed) of Project Brochure (At least 250 receivers per country)	Dissemination (electronic or printed) of Project Brochure (At least 100 receivers per country)	Dissemination (electronic or printed) of Project Brochure (At least 100 receivers per country)	Dissemination (electronic or printed) of Project Brochure (At least 100 receivers per country)
OUTCOMES INFOGRAPHIC	-	-	-	Development and distribution of Outcomes Infographic (At least 300 receivers per country)
ROLL-UP	-	Creation of Project Roll-up and display of it in partners' events	Display of Roll-up in partners' events	Display of Roll-up in partners' events
TWITTER account	Development of Twitter Account. 20 tweets, 50 followers	20 tweets, 100 followers	20 tweets, 150 followers	30 tweets, 200 followers
LINKEDIN page	Development of Linkedin page. 20 posts, 50 connections	20 posts, 100 connections	20 posts, 150 connections	30 posts, 200 connections
Notice Board	Development of the Notice Board and display in partners premises	-	-	-
Presentation on conferences, workshops, food and feed sector dedicated events	At least 10 presentations from the whole partnership	At least 10 presentations from the whole partnership	At least 10 presentations from the whole partnership	At least 15 presentations from the whole partnership

Publishing in journals, international congresses, newspapers and magazines written in the consumers language	1 article publication in newspaper or magazine per country	2 article publications in newspapers or magazines per country	2 article publications in newspapers or magazines per country	3 article publications in newspaper or magazine per country & 6 articles in scientific journals and international scientific congresses
Electronic info-sheets on selected results to be disseminated	-	-	-	1 info-sheet per case study translated in national languages
Demonstration workshops	-	-	-	3 Demonstration workshops at region level (Spain, Greece & Egypt) (At least 15 participants per country) 1 Demonstration workshops at Mediterranean level (World Rural Forum) (At least 40 participants)
Networking with other projects and initiatives	Recording of relevant projects and initiatives (At least 10 projects and initiatives)	Update of relevant projects and initiatives list. Networking activities (At least 3 per year)	Update of relevant projects and initiatives list. Networking activities (At least 3 per year)	Update of relevant projects and initiatives list. Networking activities (At least 5 per year)

6.2 Monitoring tool of dissemination & communication activities

In order to monitor and record all dissemination activities, SEVT developed a Global Dissemination Report, namely a Dissemination Excel file in project Teams Drive (Annex: Table 8 & Table 9) where all partners register their dissemination activities providing all the necessary information (date, place, topic, targeted audience, obtained feedback) related to their participation in events, fairs, workshops, conferences, and finally scientific publication in Open access or SCI journals. This tool is used not only for reporting the performed but also the upcoming dissemination activities in terms as a calendar (Annex; Table 10 & Table 11). The

partners have to record their actions by themselves but SEVT also sent every six months a reminder to do it so. SEVT, as partner in charge for this action prepared the annual dissemination reports, where all the dissemination actions are resumed.

Furthermore, in this tool the Advisory Board meetings and Demonstration Workshops were also reported.

6.3 Monitoring tool of networking activities

In order to monitor and record all networking activities, SEVT developed a Networking Report, namely an Excel file in project Teams Drive (Annex: Table 12), where all partners register their networking activities with relevant projects providing all the necessary information (date, project, type of synergy, description of the synergy). This tool is used not only for reporting the performed but also the upcoming networking activities in terms as a calendar (Annex: Table 12).

6.4 Evaluation of the effectiveness of NEWFEED Communication and Dissemination Plan According to § 6.1 and Table 6, the effectiveness of the NEWFEED Communication and Dissemination Plan is evaluated every year during the lifetime of the project.

In the present deliverable, effectiveness until M48 is presented in order to assess how many and which KPI's were achieved (Table 7).

Table 7: KPIs achieved until M48 and relevant comments.

Communication Activity	KPIs set for Year 3	KPIs set for Year 4	KPIs achieved (Yes/No)	Comments
Visual Project identity (logo, Presentation templates, etc)	Revise visual identity if necessary	Revise visual identity if necessary	N/A	Final Logo as well as presentation & deliverable templates were created during 1 st Year.
Project website & Partners' websites	Update the website & the partners webpages	Update the website & the partners webpages	YES	Newfeed website is updated with the latest news. AZTI , SEVT , NTUA , NEIKER , UAGA , UOWM , METU , HUSD , SDF , ELGO-DIMITRA have added a relevant section
PRESS RELEASES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 for Demonstration Workshops (they will be developed from the organizers of the Workshops) 1 for the communication of the project outcomes (it will be developed by SEVT in collaboration with AZTI, it will be sent to all partners to disseminate it in each national language) 		YES	The 3RD Press Release have been published & translated in Greek , Spanish , Turkish , Egyptian .

PRESS KIT FOR MEDIA	Update of the Press Kit with the results of the project	Update of the Press Kit with the results of the project	YES	The Press Kit has been updated with Project results.
NEWSLETTER	1 Newsletter (At least 250 receivers per country)	1 Newsletter (At least 250 receivers per country)	YES	The 2ND , 3RD and 4TH newsletter have been uploaded to NEWFEED website and social media as well as disseminated via partners channels.
Project Brochure	Dissemination (electronic or printed) of Project Brochure (At least 100 receivers per country)	Dissemination (electronic or printed) of Project Brochure (At least 100 receivers per country)	YES	Project brochure was created. Dissemination of the brochure was carried out via NEWFEED website and via events that took place during the Project's lifetime.
OUTCOMES INFOGRAPHIC	-	Development and distribution of Outcomes Infographic (At least 300 receivers per country)	YES	Info-graphic has been uploaded to Newfeed's website and disseminated to the Partners and their networks.
ROLL-UP	Display of Roll-up in partners' events	Display of Roll-up in partners' events	YES	The roll-up was created and uploaded it to Website . Display of the roll-up was carried out to several events. Demonstration Workshops, FOOD EXPO 2025, SEVT's General Assembly, Eco-Innovative Food Products, ECOTROPHELIA 2025 etc.
TWITTER account	20 tweets, 150 followers	30 tweets, 200 followers	YES	118 tweets, 212 followers
LINKEDIN page	20 posts, 150 connections	30 posts, 200 connections	YES	>30 posts, 1,018 followers, 500+ connections
Presentation on conferences, workshops, food and feed sector dedicated events	At least 10 presentations from the whole partnership	At least 15 presentations from the whole partnership	YES	Presentation and dissemination of NEWFEED project was carried out in several conferences, workshops and events such as: 4th International Animal Nutrition Congress , 11th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management , 75th EAAP Annual Meeting , 12th International Conference on

				Sustainable Solid Waste Management Paphos, Cyprus, 25 - 28 JUNE 2025 , R&I for a Competitive Green Transition etc.
Publishing in journals, international congresses, newspapers and magazines written in the consumers language.	2 article publications in newspapers or magazines per country	3 article publications in newspaper or magazine per country & 6 articles in scientific journals and international scientific congresses	YES	6 scientific papers published in magazines, as well as 15 scientific publications by AZTI, NTUA, HUSD, METU, UOWM and ELGO-DIMITRA in conferences in Rhodes and Florence
Electronic info-sheets on selected results to be disseminated	-	1 info-sheet per case study translated in national languages	YES	Info-sheet has been uploaded to Newfeed's website and translated to national languages.
Demonstration workshops	-	3 Demonstration workshops at region level (Spain, Greece & Egypt) (At least 15 participants per country) 1 Demonstration workshops at Mediterranean level (World Rural Forum) (At least 40 participants)	YES	Demonstration Workshops were conducted and disseminated as initially scheduled.
Networking with other projects and initiatives	Update of relevant projects and initiatives list. Networking activities (At least 3 per year)	Update of relevant projects and initiatives list. Networking activities (At least 5 per year)	YES	Networking activities were organized with similar European projects, such as WASTELESS , EXCEL4MED , CIRC FOR BIO , LANDFEED & SEA2LAND etc

*Specific information are provided in the “NEWFEED Dissemination & Communication reporting” Excel file that was created and used as a monitoring tool (see § 6.2 and Annex).

7. Communication, Dissemination & Publicity rules

7.1 Publicity Rules for PRIMA contribution

The communication and dissemination activities and publications in the project, including the project website, have a specific statement which indicates that the project has received Community research funding and display the PRIMA logo. When displayed in association with a logo, the PRIMA logo is given appropriate prominence. All publications shall include the following statement:

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's PRIMA Program for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration under grant agreement n°2013.

All projects need to observe a series of obligatory publicity rules and branding guidelines for all their communication actions. These requirements are laid down in the Annex XII of the Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 and the Annex I of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) No 821/2014. The fundamental principle is that project partners must inform the public and all those involved in the operation about the assistance received from the European Union. EU flag and PRIMA logo illustrative elements must be clearly and visibly displayed in all published materials and/or activities addressed to the public.

These obligations stand for:

- printed publications: reports, promotional handouts;
- audio-visual: videos, audio podcasts, channels;
- digital or electronic materials (websites, web tools, videos, podcast, etc.);
- events (e.g., on PPT presentations, agendas, bags and other conference material);
- Stationery and office materials.

7.2 Internal Rules for publication

To assure the protection of intellectual property rights, it is important to organize the circulation of a dissemination document, where project outcomes are published. When the included information to be disseminated is subjected to IPR, the Dissemination focusing the transfer of knowledge or project results, falls under de "D5.2 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of the project results" that will define the strategies to transfer and/or exploit the results.

8. Annex

Table 8. Dissemination and communication activities through events, articles, press releases, events until M48.

DATE	PARTNER	TYPE OF ACTIVITY	TITLE OF THE ACTIVITY	GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE	MAIN AUDIENCE	NUMBER OF PERSONS	OTHER AUDIENCE	NUMBER OF PERSONS	LINK TO WEBSITE/ DOCUMENT
At least month and year	Select from list	Select from list	Title & very short description of the activity	select from list	select from list		select from list		
7/1/2021	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			
7/1/2021	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project at SEVT website	National	Food, feed and livestock companies		Scientific community		https://www.sevt.gr/gr/european-programs/GMKP/newfeed
7/1/2021	SEVT	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Media / Press		Citizens / society		https://www.sevt.gr/userfiles/files/PR%20SEVT-New%20european%20projects.pdf
7/13/2021	AZTI	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Media / Press		Citizens / society		
7/14/2021	AZTI	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Trabajan para convertir subproductos de la industria alimentaria en piensos	National	Citizens / society				https://efs.efeservicios.com/texto/trabajan-convertir-subproductos-industria-alimentaria-piensos/55006620058
9/1/2021	ELGO-DIMITRA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project at RIAS website	National	Food, feed and livestock companies		Citizens / society		https://www.rias.gr/epistimonikes-sinergias/
7/23/2021	UOWM	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Scientific		Scientific community		https://rc.uowm.gr/?p=64425

					commun ity			
7/23/2021	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies		Citizens / society	https://www.uaga.eus/uaga-participa-en-el-proyecto-de-innovacion-prima-newfeed-que-busca-aprovechar-los-subproductos-de-la-industria-alimentaria-como-alimentacion-animal/
7/26/2021	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	UAGA participa en el proyecto de innovación PRIMA NEWFEED que busca aprovechar los subproductos de la industria alimentaria como alimentación animal	National			Citizens / society	https://www.agronewscastillayleon.com/uaga-participa-en-el-proyecto-de-innovacion-prima-newfeed-que-busca-aprovechar-los-subproductos-de
7/29/2021	BAIGORRI	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Bodegas Baigorri participa en un proyecto para aprovechar los desperdicios del raspón de uva	National			Citizens / society	Un proyecto para aprovechar los desperdicios del raspón de la uva (tecnovino.com)
7/30/2021	BAIGORRI	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Bodegas Baigorri, bajo los cimientos de la economía circular y la sostenibilidad	National			Citizens / society	Bodegas Baigorri, bajo los cimientos de la economía circular (nuevecuatrouno.com)
8/26/2021	UOWM	Press release	https://www.uowm.gr/epikairota/deltia-typoy/enarxi-toy-ergoy-prima-newfeed	National	Scientific community		Scientific community	https://www.uowm.gr/epikairota/deltia-typoy/enarxi-toy-ergoy-prima-newfeed
8/26/2021	UOWM	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	Local/Regional			Citizens / society	https://kozan.gr/archives/359445
8/26/2021	UOWM	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	Local/Regional			Citizens / society	https://www.prlogos.gr/%CF%83%CE%B5-%CE%AD%CE%BD%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9%CE%BD%CE%BF%CF%84%CF%8C%CE%BC%CE%BF-%CE%AD%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%BF-%CE%BC-%CF%84%CE%AF%CF%84%CE%BB%CE%BF-prima-newfeed-%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CF%84/
8/26/2021	UOWM	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock		Citizens / society	http://www.floriniotika.gr/2021/08/primanewfeed.html

					companies			
8/26/2021	UOWM	Social Media (Twitter & LinkedIn)	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Scientific community		Citizens / society	https://www.uowm.gr/epikairota/deltia-typoy/enarxi-toy-ergoy-prima-newfeed/
8/31/2021	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies		Citizens / society	https://www.uaga.eu/proyecto/prima-newfeed-aprovechamiento-de-subproductos-de-industria-alimentaria-para-alimentacion-animal-2021-2025/
9/1/2021	CESFAC	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Cesfac participa en el proyecto PRIMA-Newfeed	National	Food, feed and livestock companies		Food, feed and livestock companies	https://cesfac.es/images/MundoCesfac/pdf/53_mundo_CESFAC.pdf
9/26/2021	AZTI	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Aprovechan subproductos de la industria para mejorar la alimentación animal	National	Food, feed and livestock companies		Food, feed and livestock companies	https://revistaalimentaria.es/ganaderia/mundo-animal/aprovechan-subproductos-de-la-industria-para-mejorar-la-alimentacion-animal
11/1/2021	NTUA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Organizations focused on environmental protection		Public Authorities	https://eedsa.gr/site/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/ekdosi08.pdf https://basinda.metu.edu.tr/icerik/odtuden/217
12/4/2021	METU	Press release	NEWFEED: ODTÜ Ortaklığında Yeni AB Ufuk 2020 Projesi / NEWFEED: New EU Horizon 2020 Project in partnership with METU	National	Media / Press		Citizens / society	
12/17/2021	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Develop and activities	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies		Citizens / society	https://www.uaga.eu/uaga-participa-en-el-proyecto-de-innovacion-newfeed-para-el-aprovechamiento-de-los-subproductos-de-la-industria-alimentaria-en-la-alimentacion-animal/
7/14/2021	ELGO-DIMITRA	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Description of Project aim and activities	National	Media / Press		Citizens / society	https://www.facebook.com/100063464113840/posts/216032997188836/?d=n

1/13/2022	AZTI	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Newfeed investiga subproductos de la industria alimentaria para fabricar pienso animal	National	Media / Press		Citizens / society		https://rumiantes.com/proyecto-newfeed-investiga-aprovechar-subproductos-industria-alimentaria-fabricar-pienso-animal/
1/1/2022	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Exploitation of Food Industry by-products	National	Organizations focused on environmental protection				https://eedsa.gr/site/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/ekdosi08.pdf
6/1/2022	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	SEVT ANNUAL REPORT 2021	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			https://drive.google.com/file/d/127IMNgJc8lpwchuApNBKJ6SnYSJLsDob/view
7/1/2022	SEVT	Website	Newsletter upload on SEVT site	national	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			https://www.sevt.gr/gr/european-programs-details/HMijsg/newfeed-newsletter
7/1/2022	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED newsletter promoted through SEVT e-newsletter	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			-
11/8/2022	NTUA	Event, other (organizer)	Meeting of NTUA team with representatives from an orange processing industry	Local/Regional	Investors and relevant professionals	5			-
11/24/2022	AZTI	Conference (participation)	Congreso Nacional de Medioambiente (CONAMA 2022). Presentation of NEWFEED project in a Panel of experts in a Technical Session-41 Innovation in circular economy: strategies	National	Investors and relevant professionals	100	Public Authorities		http://www.conama2022.org/web/generico.php?idpagina=&lang=es&menu=370&id=330&op=view

			and new business models.						
12/5/2022	UOWM	Event, other (organizer)	Regional Innovation days	Local/Regional	Citizens / society	220	Public Authorities	20	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1qo1xKDv0Kmusl8PXvGUxJBfq_AYlziA?usp=share_link
2-5/2/2023	ELGO-DIMITRA	Exhibition/Fair	Zootechnia ' International Trade Fair on Livestock and Poultry	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	45000	Public Authorities	1000	https://www.zootechnia-expo.gr/en/
08/2/2023	UOWM	Event, other (organizer)	Regional Innovation days Kozani	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	300	Scientific community	20	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ypQpJaRble2GpLkKCON4iyIXIAFXIDHI?usp=share_link
15/2/2023	UAGA	Workshop (organizer)	2nd Advisory board meeting of the NEWFEED project	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	20	Investors and relevant professionals		https://newfeed-prima.eu/advisory-board-2/
17/2/2023	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Develop and activities	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	100	Citizens / society	500	https://www.uaga.eus/uaga-participa-en-la-2a-reunion-del-comite-asesor-del-proyecto-de-innovacion-newfeed/
22/2/2023	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Develop and activities	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	100	Citizens / society	500	https://twitter.com/UAGAiNFO/status/1628303784404217856?cxt=HHwWgMCz_cXq8pgtAAAA
18-20/3/2023	SEVT	Exhibition/Fair	FOOD EXPO GREECE	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	500	Public Authorities	500	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ghurMczskJat7Bsp7Suklmt47B43nSee?usp=sharing
01/4/2023	HUSD	Workshop (participation)	Farm Manager and Scientific, logistic and high executive persons	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	10	Food, feed and livestock companies	10	

8-9/5/2023	HUSD	Conference (organizer)	ENI-CBCMED “WEF-CAP Multi-stakeholders Capitalization” conference organized by RSS (Jordan) and ECITD (Egypt), Alexandria- ORAL PRESENTATION OF NEWFEED	Local/Regional	Scientific community	200	Investors and relevant professionals	50	
25/5/2023	AZTI	Event, other (participation)	EU Food & Loss Platform - Subgroup Action & Implementation - Title: "Key aspects for the transformation of former foodstuffs into animal feed or high value products" - Presentation of NEWFEED project - Author: David San Martin from AZTI.	International	Public Authorities	150	Public Authorities	???	https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-05/fw_eu-platform_20230525_sub-ai_pres-05.pdf
05/6/2023	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Project activities and progress information	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	500	Citizens / society	500	https://www.uaga.eus/primeros-resultados-del-proyecto-newfeed-para-el-aprovechamiento-de-subproductos-de-la-industria-alimentaria-para-alimentacion-animal/
08-10/6/2023	ELGO-DIMITRA	Exhibition/Fair	Forward Green Exhibition – Adapting Circular Economy held in Thessaloniki (Greece) ORAL PRESENTATION OF NEWFEED	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	200	Scientific community	500	
12/6/2023	SEVT	Event, other (organizer)	SEVT General Assembly	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	90	Scientific community	10	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1OMUYIskkZPGlpJWYImTAE2Qww_o_to5I?usp=sharing
12/6/2023	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	SEVT ANNUAL REPORT 2022	National	Food, feed and livestock	60			2022

14/6/2023	HUSD	Other (specify in the following column)	make a presentation in the PED meeting to inform the University community about the project	Local/Regional	Scientific community	120	Investors and relevant professionals	20	
21-24/06/2023	AZTI	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	CHANIA 2023 "10th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management " - Title: Biorefinery of grape stem to obtain a sugar-rich liquor for food applications and an ingredient for animal feed - Author: Jone Ibarruri from AZTI	International	Scientific community	100	Scientific community		
07/07/2023	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Project activities and progress information	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	500	Citizens / society	500	https://www.uaga.eus/uaga-participa-en-la-reunion-anual-del-proyecto-newfeed-para-aprovechar-subproductos-alimentarios-como-ingredientes-para-alimentacion-animal/
25/07/2023	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED 2nd annual project meeting in Athens	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1YYF471E7XwqPsHw4oBXRUpHYFgiNVKwK/view?usp=drive_link
08/09/2023	ELGO-DIMITRA	Event, other (participation)	AGROTOUR - Smart livestock: Project results dissemination - Presentation of the NEWFEED project as part of the research activity of the research team	National	Food, feed and livestock companies				
08/09/2023	UOWM	Event, other (organizer)	AGROTOUR - Smart livestock: Project results dissemination - Presentation of the NEWFEED project as part of the research	Local/Regional	Scientific community	100	Citizens / society	20	https://agrotour.uowm.gr/2023/09/06/imerida_kozani/

			activity of the research team						
13/10/2023	HUSD	Workshop (organizer)	2-day hybrid workshop with FAO, Model Egypt	Local/Regional	Investors and relevant professionals	20			https://newfeed-prima.eu/case-study-3-fao-workshop/
01/11/2023	HUSD	Event, other (participation)	National exhibition about waste management product alongside the Social Initiative Forum	International	Scientific community		Food, feed and livestock companies		https://newfeed-prima.eu/case-study-3-exhibition-about-waste-management-products/
13/11/2023	SEVT	Event, other (organizer)	FOOD TECH 2023, "New standards in Packaging and Packaging Waste for the Food & Drink Industry - Developments & Perspectives" & "New food trends & new food products"	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	30	Scientific community	20	https://www.sevt.gr/en/news-details/HM-Psw/foodtech-global-pack-2023-sevt-parallel-events
30/11/2023	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Newfeed social media banner	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iuXYKNckOixEFAiyrbgAa6hzqdm2Ut/view?usp=drive_link
01/02/2024	ELGO-DIMITRA	Event, other (participation)	AGROTICA 2024 1-4 Feb.	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	500	Citizens / society	20	https://newfeed-prima.eu/case-study-2-agrotica-expo-2024/
29/2-3/3/2024	METU	Conference (participation) * without proceedings	Animal Nutrition Congress -Antalya	International	Scientific community	300	Investors and relevant professionals		https://www.hayvanbesleme.org.tr/2023/09/03/4th-international-animal-nutrition-congress
9-11/03/2024	SEVT	Exhibition/Fair	FOOD EXPO GREECE 2024	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	500	Public Authorities	500	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1srWZDk60ob3Xtf4iilFLiymE8gMHH75nO?usp=drive_link

15/03/2024	UAGA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project: Develop and activities, 2nd press release	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	100	Citizens / society	500	https://www.uaga.eus/21-de-marzo-jornada-de-demostracion-del-proyecto-newfeed-en-el-que-participa-uaga/
19/03/2024	UOWM	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Presentation of the YouTube video about Case Study 2	Local/Regional	Citizens / society		Citizens / society		https://kozan.gr/archives/542769
19/03/2024	UOWM	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Presentation of the YouTube video about Case Study 2	Local/Regional	Citizens / society		Citizens / society		https://neafiorina.gr/2024/03/scholi-geoponikon-epistimon-axiopoisi-yppoiouton-tis-viomichanias-paragogis-chymon-portokali-gia-tin-paragogi-veltioimenon-systatikon-zootrofon-gia-mikra-mirykastika-provata/
20/03/2024	UOWM	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Presentation of the YouTube video about Case Study 2	Local/Regional	Citizens / society		Citizens / society		http://www.floriotika.gr/2024/03/blog-post_995.html
20/03/2024	UOWM	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Presentation of the YouTube video about Case Study 2	National	Citizens / society		Citizens / society		https://www.ertnews.gr/perifereiakoi-stathmoi/florina/dytiki-makedonia-symmetoxi-tis-sxolis-geoponias-stin-aksiopoisi-portokaliou-gia-paragogi-zootrofon/?fbclid=IwAR1-UptZRQECjCWHI1Pse1seHsxy_gFP4t7E_QHXAXsRIARMH KCuNJsIxCO
21/03/2024	UOWM	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Presentation of the YouTube video about Case Study 2	Local/Regional	Citizens / society		Citizens / society		https://grevenamedia.gr/dytiki-makedonia-symmetochitis-scholis-geoponias-stin-axiopoisi-portokalioy-gia-paragogi-zootrofon/
21/03/2024	ELGO-DIMITRA	Newsletter	Newsletter upload on Institute site	National	Scientific community		Citizens / society		https://www.rias.gr/2%ce%bf-%ce%b4%ce%b5%ce%bb%cf%84%ce%af%ce%bf-%cf%84%cf%8d%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%85-%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%85-%ce%b5%cf%81%ce%b5%cf%85%ce%bd%ce%b7%cf%84%ce%b9%ce%ba%ce%bf%cf%8d-%ce%ad%cf%81%ce%b3%ce%bf%cf%85-newfeed/
21/03/2024	ELGO-DIMITRA	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Presentation of the YouTube video about Case Study 2	National	Scientific community		Citizens / society		https://www.rias.gr/newfeed-%ce%b1%ce%be%ce%b9%ce%bf%cf%80%ce%bf%ce%af%ce%b7%cf%83%ce%b7-%cf%85%cf%80%ce%bf%cf%80%cf%81%ce%bf%cf%8a%cf%8c%ce%bd%cf%84%cf%89%ce%bd-%cf%84%ce%b7%cf%82-%ce%b2%ce%b9%ce%bf%ce%bc%ce%b7%cf%87/

21/03/2024	AZTI	Press release	NEWFEED Project: Develop and activities, 2nd press release	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500	Citizens / society	500	https://www.azti.es/en/newfeed-demonstration-workshops/
27/03/2024	UOWM	Broadcasting (e.g. TV or radio)	Presentation of the NewFeed Project in National TV (ERT 3) in a news and current affairs programme showing particular news of the regional parts of Greece	National	Citizens / society		Citizens / society		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7BtY8Ui1nLU
29/03/2024	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED newsletter promoted through SEVT e-newsletter	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			#6_SEVT_Newsletter_March2024.pdf
16/04/2024	AZTI	Conference (participation) * without proceedings	Food4Future 2024 - Bilbao Foodtech World Summit	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	100	Investors and relevant professionals	500	https://www.expofoodtech.com/agenda-sessions/3600-sustainability-innovation-collaboration-and-efficiency-20240416/
02/12/2023	HUSD	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Egyptian J. Nutrition and Feeds	National	Food, feed and livestock companies				https://ejnf.journals.ekb.eg/issue_41143_45068.html
June 19-22, 2024	METU	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	11 th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024	International	Scientific community	950 (physical presence + online)	Organizations focused on environmental protection		https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/
June 19-22, 2024	AZTI	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management,	International	Scientific	950 (physical)	Organizations focused on		https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/

			Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)		community	presence + online)	environmental protection		
June 19-22, 2024	ELGO-DIMITRA	Conference (organizer) *only with proceedings	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)	International	Scientific community	950 (physical presence + online)	Organizations focused on environmental protection		https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/
13/06/2025	UOWM	Conference (participation)	Orange peels as a feed ingredient in lactating ewes: Effects on Yoghurt Quality (in Greek)	National	Scientific community				
June 19-22, 2024	HUSD	Conference (organizer) *only with proceedings	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)	International	Scientific community	950 (physical presence + online)	Organizations focused on environmental protection		https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/
21-24/06/2023	METU	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	CHANIA 2023 "10th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management	International	Scientific community	about 800	Organizations focused on environmental protection		https://chania2023.uest.gr/

01/09/2024	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED Project was promoted through SEVT e-newsletter	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	500			https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1JxPgHSY5jihZTwdwlZupGiYP1qS7q9WW
18/10/2024	UOWM	Event, other (participation)	Science and Research Day at the University of Western Macedonia	Local/Regional	Scientific community	about 400	Citizens / society	about 200	https://www.uowm.gr/epikairota/deltia-typoy/imera-epistimis-kai-ereynas-sto-pdm/
28/01/2025	AZTI	Event, other (participation)	Eighth SFS-MED webinar - COORDINATING LOCAL AND NATIONAL ACTIONS TO REDUCE FOOD LOSS AND WASTE IN MEDITERRANEAN CITIES	International	Scientific community	100	Public Authorities	100	content
06/03/2025	AZTI	Conference (participation) * without proceedings	7th International circular economy meeting - Avancing towards resource efficiency	National	Scientific community	200	Public Authorities	200	7ª edición Encuentro Internacional Economía Circular. 6 y 7 marzo Entradas, Varias fechas Eventbrite
26/03/2025	AZTI	Workshop (organizer)	NUEVAS MATERIAS PRIMAS EN ALIMENTACIÓN ANIMAL	National	Scientific community	100	Investors and relevant professionals	100	https://www.feriazaragoza.es/figan
02/04/2025	AZTI	Conference (participation) * without proceedings	Basque Circular summit	National	Scientific community	200	Public Authorities	200	https://basquecircularsummit.eus/
13/05/2025	AZTI	Conference (participation) * without proceedings	Food4Future 2025	International	Scientific community	100	Public Authorities	100	https://www.expofoodtech.com/

					community				
25/06/2025	AZTI	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management - CYPRUS 2025	International	Scientific community	1000	Public Authorities	1000	https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/
25/06/2025	HUSD	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management - CYPRUS 2025	International	Scientific community	1000	Public Authorities	1000	https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/
25/06/2025	NTUA	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management - CYPRUS 2025	International	Scientific community	1000	Public Authorities	1000	https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/
25/06/2025	METU	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management - CYPRUS 2025	International	Scientific community	1000	Public Authorities	1000	https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/
25/06/2025	NTUA	Conference (participation) *only with proceedings	12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management - CYPRUS 2025	International	Scientific community	1000	Public Authorities	1000	https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/
30/10/2024	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Article on SEVT's monthly newsletter about NEWFEED's 3rd annual meeting	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	50			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1TZfsezeEGV7TO_CZfx6fKjeyBNLg6S15/view?usp=drive_link

20/12/2024	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	NEWFEED project promoted through banner on SEVT's monthly newsletter	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	50			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L8Vxf7VyJaDswYnMDZdtw-ienkPHPmzw/view?usp=drive_link
12/02/2025	SEVT	Workshop (organizer)	Dissemination of NEWFEEDS project on ECOTROPHELIA 2025 THE WORKSHOP	Local/Regional	Scientific community	50			https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1GyDkMZ7DoBJg02nKDDxMvBnI72cgl2jU?usp=drive_link
27/02/2025	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Article on SEVT's monthly newsletter about NEWFEED's 4th annual meeting	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	50			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1SPmYyni90fmPWU5PzCWExCVZDMRANfei/view?usp=drive_link
8-10/03/2025	SEVT	Event, other (participation)	Dissemination of NEWFEEDS project through SEVT's booth on FOODDEXPO 2025	International	Food, feed and livestock companies	>500			https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1zCKBter_d6x6oy61fR170QpE4SfuWxVi?usp=drive_link
31/03/2025	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Article on SEVT's monthly newsletter about NEWFEED's webinar	National	Food, feed and livestock companies	50			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1NRkyOv7K9Wuf85sII4seDvUNNgOnM6F-/view?usp=drive_link
28/05/2025	SEVT	Article (Newsletter, newspaper, info-site, etc)	Article on SEVT's monthly newsletter about NEWFEED's webinar	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	>500			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1XCk3UzJZtXe3D0cD7O1D2TLYOP6yYou/view?usp=drive_link
14/05/2025	SEVT	Event, other (organizer)	GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2025	Local/Regional	Food, feed and livestock companies	200			https://drive.google.com/file/d/1D7pYvwrNoAGHe2yixWXxvVUGhyJw7QD0/view?usp=drive_link

13/06/2025	UOWM	Event, other (organiser)	2nd Symposium of Research Projects of UOWM	Local/Regional	Scientific community	200	Citizens/communitiy	https://padlet.com/2symposiouowm/2-z579x4qrpjla2aiz
17-18/6/2025	SEVT	Event, other (organizer)	Eco-Innovative Food Products, ECOTROPHELIA 2025	National	Scientific community, students	200		https://newfeed-prima.eu/newfeed-sevt-2/
23-24/6/2025	AZTI	Event (Participant)	R&I for a Competitive Green Transition	International	Scientific communities, EU authorities	1000		https://newfeed-prima.eu/research-and-innovation-for-a-competitive-green-transition/ https://www.linkedin.com/in/newfeed-project-2a3795220/recent-activity/all/
25-28/6/2025	ALL PARTNERS	Conference (Participants)	12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management	International	Scientific communities, EU authorities	1000		https://newfeed-prima.eu/12th-international-conference-on-sustainable-solid-waste-management/ https://www.linkedin.com/in/newfeed-project-2a3795220/recent-activity/all/

Table 9. Scientific publications until M48.

PARTNER	TYPE OF SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION	TITLE OF THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION	AUTHORS	TITLE OF THE JOURNAL OR EQUIVALENT
Select from list	Select from list	TITLE OF THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION		
NTUA	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Alternative valorisation pathways for orange peel waste	D. Kousoulis, G. Zantis, K. Moustakas, E.M. Barampouti, S. Mai	9TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT, 15-18 JUNE 2022, CORFU, GREECE
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Hydrolysis strategies for the valorisation of Grape stems to improve their value in ruminant feeds	D. San Martin, J. Ibarruri, N. Luengo, J. Ferrer, A. Garcia-Rodriguez, I. Goiri, R. Atxaerandio, J. Zufía, E. Sáez de Cámara, B. Iñarra	9TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT, 15-18 JUNE 2022, CORFU, GREECE
NTUA	Article in Journal	Upcycled Animal Feed: Sustainable Solution to Orange Peels Waste	Christina Andrianou, Konstantinos Passadis, Dimitris Malamis, Konstantinos Moustakas, Sofia Mai, Elli Maria Barampouti	Sustainability
HUSD	Article in Journal	The effect of adding fermented olive cake with and without herbal aromatic plants to broilers chicken diet.	H. A.F. Rahmy, Salma, N. El-Deen, Fatma, M. Abosamra, A. M. Khaled.	Egyptian J. Nutrition and Feeds 2023, 26(3), 411-418.
METU	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Environmental Sustainability Assessment of Valorizing Orange Peels Waste in Animal Feed Production	F.B. Dilek, E. M. Barampouti, S. Mai, K. Moustakas, D. Malamis, D.S. Martin, U. Yetis	10TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT, 21-24 JUNE 2023, CRETE, GREECE
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Biorefinery of grape stem to obtain a sugar-rich liquor for food applications and an ingredient for animal feed (ORAL in CHANIA 2023)	D. San Martin, J. Ibarruri, N. Luengo, J. Ferrer, A. Garcia-Rodriguez, I. Goiri, R. Atxaerandio, J. Zufía, E. Sáez de Cámara, B. Iñarra.	10TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT, 21-24 JUNE 2023, CRETE, GREECE

HUSD	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Fermentation strategies for the valorizations of Olive cake to improve their nutritional value in Broiler's feeds	" H. A. F. Rahmy, S. Nour El-Deen, F. Mohamed Abosamra, A. Saied Mohamed Korayem"	10TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT, 21-24 JUNE 2023, CRETE, GREECE
NTUA	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Production of orange peel-based ingredients for dairy sheep feed in pilot scale	D. Christianides, A. Tsimeras, F. Chatzimaliakas, I. Bousoulas, M. Chatziaggelakis, K. Passadis, K. Moustakas, E.M. Barampouti, S. Mai	10TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT, 21-24 JUNE 2023, CRETE, GREECE
AZTI	Article in Journal	Evaluation of Valorisation Strategies to Improve Grape Stems' Nutritional Value as an Ingredient for Ruminants' Diets	San Martin, D.; Ibarruri, J.; Luengo, N.; Ferrer, J.; García-Rodríguez, A.; Goiri, I.; Atxaerandio, R.; Zufía, J.; Sáez de Cámara, E.; Iñarra, B.	Sustainability
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Optimization of bioethanol production from a sugar-rich liquor and a functional animal feed ingredient obtained in the biorefinery scheme of grape stem	J. Ibarruri, B. Iñarra, A. Bikandi, A. Salvarrey, N. Luengo, J. Ferrer, J. Zufía, M. Gutierrez, D. San Martin	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Valorization of grape stems as a functional ingredient in ruminant diets	D. San Martin, J. Ibarruri, A. García-Rodríguez, I. Goiri, R. Atxaerandio, N. Luengo, J. Ferrer, J. Zufía, M. Gutierrez, E. Sáez de Cámara, B. Iñarra	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)
ELGO-DIMITRA	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Orange peels as a secondary feedstuff for dairy sheep	MA. Karatzia, V. Kotsampasi, Z. Basdagianni, S. Mai, EM. Barampouti, E. Kasapidou	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)
HUSD	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	The Impact of Broiler Feed on Growth and Performance by Valorisation of Olive Cake as By-product in the Ration	H. A. F. Rahmy, S. Nour El-Deen, F. Mohamed Abosamra, A. Kaled	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)
METU	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Life Cycle Assessment of Valorizing Olive Cake Waste in Animal Feed Production	F.B. Dilek, H. A. F. Rahmy, S. Nour El-Deen, F. Mohamed Abosamra, A. M. Khaled, D. San Martin, U. Yetis	11th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Rhodes 2024 (https://rhodes2024.uest.gr/)
METU	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Environmental Sustainability of Valorizing Food Waste in Animal Feed	F.B. Dilek, D. San Martin, J. Ibarruri, B. Iñarra, U. Yetis	4th International Animal Nutrition Congress

		Production- Case of Grape Stem		
UOWM	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Dietary supplementation of orange peel ingredient in lactating ewes: effect on yoghurt physicochemical characteristics	Kasapidou, E., Papatzimos, G., Mitlianga, P., Basdagianni, Z., Mai, S., Barampouti, E.M., & Karatzia, M.A.	75th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Animal Science (https://eaap2024.org/) - Book of Abstracts
UOWM	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Dietary supplementation of orange peel ingredient in lactating ewes: effect on yoghurt sensory characteristics	Kasapidou, E., Mitlianga, P., Basdagianni, Z., Papatzimos, G., Mai, S., Barampouti, E.M., & Karatzia, M.A.	75th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Animal Science (https://eaap2024.org/) - Book of Abstracts
ELGO-DIMITRA	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Utilization of orange peels as a high value secondary feedstuff for dairy sheep	Karatzia, M.A., Kotsampasi, V., Basdagianni, Z., Mai, S., Barampouti, E.M., & Kasapidou, E.	75th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Animal Science (https://eaap2024.org/) - Book of Abstracts
METU	Article in Journal	Assessing Environmental and Economic Sustainability: Valorizing Grape Stems for Animal Feed Production	Filiz B. Dilek, David San Martin, Mónica Gutierrez, Jone Ibarruri, Bruno Iñarra, Ulku Yetis	ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering
UOWM	Article in Journal	Orange Peel Feed Ingredient in Lactating Ewes: Effect on Yoghurt Chemical Composition, Fatty Acid Profile, Antioxidant Activity, Physicochemical Properties, and Sensory Quality	Kasapidou, E., Mitlianga, P., Basdagianni, Z., Papatzimos, G., Mai, S., Barampouti, E.M., Papadopoulos, V., & Karatzia, M.A.	Applied Sciences
METU	Article in Journal	Orange Peel Waste Valorization: An Integrated Assessment of Environmental and Economic Sustainability in Animal Feed Production	Filiz Bengu Dilek · Elli M. Barampouti · Sofia Mai · Konstantinos Moustakas · Dimitris Malamis · David S. Martin · Ulku Yetis	Waste and Biomass Valorization
HUSD	Article in Journal	Impact of Diets Containing Olive Cake and Herbs on Growth Performance and Carcass Traits of Broiler Chicken Through Growing Stage	Hassan Awany Fouad Rahmy, Salma Mohamed Mahmoud Noureldin, Fatma Mohamed Mostafa Abosamra, Adel Eid Mohamed Mahmoud, Adel Mohamed Khaled Elsaid and Abdallah Sayed Mohamed Korayem	
HUSD	Article in Journal	Statistical Optimization of Solid-State Fermentation by Aspergillus oryzae for	Abdalla Sayed Mohamed Korayem, Fafy A. Mohammed, Samah H. Abu-Hussien, Fatma M. Abosamra, Salma Nour El-Dein, Hassan. A.F. Rahmy.	Wiley Scientifica Volume 2025

		Valorization of Olive Cake and Its Application as a Poultry Feed.		
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	NEWFEED - Turn food industry by-products into secondary feedstuffs via circular-economy schemes.	D. San Martin	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Assessment of the use of grape stem from wineries as a second-generation feedstuff to produce a new feed ingredient for ruminants (dairy sheep and cattle).	J. Ibarruri	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)
AZTI	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Business Models for the Circular Economy: Valorisation of Food Industry By-products to produce Animal Feed Ingredients.	B. Iñarra	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)
AZTI & METU	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Comparative Life Cycle Costing and Life Cycle Assessment of Animal Feed Ingredient Production from Grape Stems, Orange Peels, and Olive Cake.	F.B. Dilek, D.S. Martin, U. Yetis	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)
NTUA	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Orange peels as a second-generation feedstuff to produce a new feed ingredient for dairy sheep.	S. Mai, E.M. Barampouti, K. Moustakas, M.A. Karatzia, E. Kasapidou	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)
HUSD	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Valorization of Olive Cake as a By-product in Broiler Ration and its Effect on Growth, Carcass Characteristics and Blood Parameters.	Hassan. A. F. Rahmy, S. Nour El-Deen, F. M. Abosamra, A.E. M. Mahmoud, A. M. Khaled2, A. S. M. Korayema	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)

HUSD	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Valorization of Olive Cake as a By-product in Broiler Ration and its Effect on Growth, Carcass Characteristics and Blood Parameters.	Hassan. A. F. Rahmy, S. Nour El-Deen, F. M. Abosamra, A.E. M. Mahmoud, A. M. Khaled2, A. S. M. Korayema	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)
SEVT	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Social assessment of turning food industry by-products into secondary feedstuffs via circular – economy schemes	E. Xaxiri, E. Maravelia, El. Tsapa, A. Gavriil, A. Kapetanakou, V. Papadimitriou, D. San Martin	12th Int. conference on sustainable solid waste management, Cyprus 2025 (https://cyprus2025.uest.gr/)

Table 10. Calendar of performed and planned networking activities with relevant projects.

Date	Project	Contact Partner	Possible synergies	Synergie	Description of completed actions and synergies
06/02/2023	WASTELESS: Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress. https://wastelesseu.com/	SEVT		exchange info about the project	A on-line discussion took place between AZTI & SEVT (representing NEWFEED) and ISEKI (representing WASTELESS) exchanging information about the projects and sharing ideas about potential synergies.
Feb-23	H2020 FoodRus: Circular Solutions for Resilient Food Systems https://www.foodrus.eu/	AZTI		exchange info about the project	The valorization strategies of each project have been compared to identify options for improvement. In turn, the preliminary results of the nutritional efficiency of the ingredients have been compared to analyze the feasibility of the project.
Mar-23	Life BREWERY: New Strategies for the Sustainability of Brewery Activity: Full Wastes Recovery for Aquaculture feed https://lifebrewery.azti.es	AZTI; RIERA		exchange info about the project	The valorization strategies of each project have been compared to identify options for improvement.
Mar-23	BBI WaSeaBi: Optimal utilization of seafood side-streams through the design of new holistic process lines https://www.waseabi.eu/	AZTI		exchange info about the project	The valorization strategies of each project have been compared to identify options for improvement.
Mar-23	H2020 Sea2Land: Producing advanced bio-based fertilizers from fisheries wastes https://sea2landproject.eu/	AZTI, NEIKER		exchange info about the project	The valorization strategies of each project have been compared to identify options for improvement.
Apr-23	Life ECOFFEED: New Strategies for the Coffee Spent Grounds Recovery as a new Raw Material for Animal Feed https://ecoffeed.azti.es/	AZTI; NEIKER; RIERA		exchange info about the project	The valorization strategies of each project have been compared to identify options for improvement. In turn, the preliminary results of the nutritional efficiency of the ingredients have been compared to analyze the feasibility of the project.
19-20/06/2023	LIFE CIRCforBIO: A circular economy system for multi-source biomass conversion to added value products.	SEVT & NTUA		exchange info about the project	The annual mtg of Newfeed took place. SEVT & NTUA participate in both projects, thus they shared information to Newfeed partners. Roll-ups and brochures were used of both projects.

	https://circforbio.eu/				
20/12/2023	WASTELESS: Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress. https://wastelesseu.com/	SEVT		share project's info or results via newsletter	WASTELESS dedicated a section in its Newsletter in December 2023 https://newfeed-prima.eu/networking/clustering-activities-958/
Dec-23	HONDORFOOD: Recovery options for food by-products in the Basque food chain	AZTI		exchange info about the project	Exchange of information on the solution implementation model and lesson learned to define the NEWFEED business model.
Dec-23	Life BREWERY: New Strategies for the Sustainability of Brewery Activity: Full Wastes Recovery for Aquaculture feed https://lifebrewery.azti.es	AZTI; RIERA		exchange info about the project	Exchange of information on the solution implementation model and lesson learned to define the NEWFEED business model.
Dec-23	BBI WaSeaBi: Optimal utilization of seafood side-streams through the design of new holistic process lines https://www.waseabi.eu/	AZTI		exchange info about the project	Exchange of information on the solution implementation model and lesson learned to define the NEWFEED business model.
Dec-23	H2020 Sea2Land: Producing advanced bio-based fertilizers from fisheries wastes https://sea2landproject.eu/	AZTI; NEIKER		exchange info about the project	Exchange of information on the solution implementation model and lesson learned to define the NEWFEED business model.
13/5/2024	LIFE CIRCforBIO: A circular economy system for multi-source biomass conversion to added value products. https://circforbio.eu/ FOLOU: Bringing knowledge and consensus to prevent and reduce Food Loss at the primary production stage https://www.folou.eu/	ALL		presentation of the project in projects' meetings, events, etc	NewFeed organized an engaging networking webinar with CIRCforBIO and FOLOU projects in order to exchange information and knowledge. https://newfeed-prima.eu/networking-webinar-highlights/

Jun-24	EUROSHEEP: Increasing production efficiency and coping with climate change, while ensuring sustainability and resilience. https://eurosheep.network/?lang=el	ELGO-DIMITRA	share project's info or results via newsletter		The project has been completed, but an effort to share NewFeed's info and results via newsletter to the mailing list of Eurosheel can be done
Jul-24	WAYSTUP: Value chains for disruptive transformation of urban biowaste into biobased products in the city context https://waystup.eu/	NTUA	share project's info or results via newsletter		The project has been completed, but an effort to share NewFeed's info and results via newsletter to the mailing list of Eurosheel can be done
Febr-25	EXCEL4MED: Production of nutritious food products and maximizing the use of food industrial by-products https://excel4med.eu/	AZTI & SEVT		exchange info about the project	Exchange of information on circular economy strategies and sustainable food production.
Mar-25	WASTELESS: Waste Quantification Solutions to Limit Environmental Stress https://wastelesseu.com/	SEVT		exchange info about the project	Share results, innovative tools, and future goals, fostering collaboration between the two EU-funded projects.
June - 25	LANDFEED: Transforming waste into sustainable biofertilisers https://www.landfeed.eu/	AZTI & SEVT		exchange info about the project	https://newfeed-prima.eu/newfeed-landfeed-sea2land-networking-webinar-joint-action-for-sustainable-food-systems/
June - 25	SEA2LAND: Producing advanced bio-based fertilizers from fisheries wastes https://sea2landproject.eu/	AZTI & SEVT		exchange info about the project	https://newfeed-prima.eu/newfeed-landfeed-sea2land-networking-webinar-joint-action-for-sustainable-food-systems/